

**University of
South Wales**
Prifysgol
De Cymru

Anti-Aging for Athletes - Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

Background: This systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to obtain an improved comprehension of the process of aging in athletes and the ways by which aging can be mitigated to increase professional longevity, this was done by investigating Telomere length.

Methods: Up until October 2023, a literature search was conducted in PubMed, Web of Science, ClinicalTrials.gov, DOAJ, Europe PubMed Central, and Scopus, yielding 27 relevant studies; 19 cohort studies were quantitatively analyzed. Subjects comprised 486 Master athletes (55.3 years), 271 elite young athletes (23.6 years), 394 Old control (53.9 years), and 318 Young controls (23.8 years). Total population: n=1469 were analyzed.

Results: Results indicate Master athletes have a Mean Telomere length of 0.290 T/S ratio greater than Old Control (95% CI [0.110, 0.470]), while Young athletes show 0.220 T/S ratio greater than Young controls (95% CI [-0.00380, 0.445]), highlighting high-level training's potential in countering aging effects. Electronic equipment & regenerative medicine lack direct anti-aging effects but aid in maintaining elite performance, potentially delaying retirement. Hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBO) and cryotherapy show promise in athlete anti-aging, requiring more trials for verification.

Conclusion: Optimal exercise selection, periodization, motivation, coping strategies, and modern electronic equipment use, enable athletes to sustain elite performance post the average competition retirement age of 34. Recommendations drawn from this literature necessitate clinical validation to counteract aging's impact on athletes.

Introduction

Aging in Athletes is accompanied by many changes leading to a decline in performance, body composition changes (Figure 1), and altered metabolism (Tanaka & Seals, 2008; Strasser et al., 2021). The reduction of maximal stroke volume, heart rate, and arteriovenous oxygen difference are among those changes, which contribute to age-related declines in maximal oxygen consumption (Tanaka & Seals, 2008). Also, aging affects the respiratory system, resulting in a decrease in lung diffusion capacity and decreased aerobic metabolic power in endurance athletes (Degens et al., 2013). According to Jokl et al., (2004), Muscle strength peaks at the end of the third decade of life. However, it starts to decline around the age of 50, with a decline rate and degree that is influenced by the physical activity level of the individual. Moreover, Sarcopenia, which is characterized by a loss in muscle mass and function represents a risk for aging athletes. (Grosicki et al., 2021).

Psychologically, Aging athletes usually face high levels of stress because of social comparisons, especially when they are about to reach the usual retirement age of 34 (Horton et al., 2019; North & Lavalley, 2004). What Horton et al., (2019) meant by social comparison is when coaches, fans, and club managers start to compare aging athletes to younger ones, making aging athletes feel disadvantaged.

However, not all athletes are affected the same, because according to Gümüşdağ & İlhan, (2022), athletes of different ages, genders, education levels, and surroundings may have evident psychological traits. Also, peak athletic performance stays relatively stable in all sports, occurring in the early to mid-30s, and the age impact on performance and recovery may be smaller than originally implied (Tanaka & Seals, 2003; Borges et al., 2016). So, it is understandable that

retiring at 34 might be too early since athletes can maintain their elite performance until 35, and the decline rate of performance after that age due to aging effects is not significant.

Scientists recognize Telomere length (TL) as an important indicator of biological aging (Ackermann & Fischer, 2019). Telomeres are repeated DNA sequences (TTAGGG) that are present at the end of chromosomes, playing an important role in maintaining the stability and integrity of the genome (Blackburn et al., 2015). Telomere shortening happens naturally during cell division, and also happens as a result of malfunctioning cells, which leads to disruption in the pace of cell division, eventually causing tissue function loss which is known as "biological aging" (Blackburn et al., 2015; Sousa-Victor et al., 2015). So, any lifestyle choice or exercise selection helping in the prolongation of the telomeres carries the potential to mitigate the aging process and increase the number of years that one can live a healthy life.

Elite athletes who represented their country in international contests or were competing professionally (Elwood et al., 2021) in their early to mid-30s, and master athletes, who are individuals aged over 35 years old and still dedicated to training, competition, and sports achievement (Kim et al., 2021) has been approached in many studies to investigate the effect of their healthy lifestyle habits on aging (Abrahin et al., 2019; Korhonen et al., 2014; Kusy and Zielinski, 2015). Their lifestyle usually enables them to have a better metabolic profile, physical fitness, and maximal oxygen uptake when compared to age-matched sedentary individuals (Kusy and Zielinski, 2015). Several studies detected that Elite and master athletes have longer telomere lengths than age-matched sedentary individuals (Abrahin et al., 2019; Aguiar et al., 2019; Aguiar et al, 2022;

Borghini et al., 2015; Denham et al., 2013; Hagman et al., 2021; LaRocca et al., 2010; Osthus et al., 2012; Rae et al., 2010; Rosa, 2020; Simoes et al., 2017). However, studies didn't specify the common factors that can contribute to aging, such as the physiological influences and the psychological aspects of aging on athletes. Also, studies didn't provide specific recommendations for athletes to mitigate aging effects through proper exercise selection, recovery, and the use of recent medical advances like Hyperbaric oxygen therapy, electronic equipment, and regenerative medicine. That is why, the aim of this systematic review and meta-analysis was to obtain an improved comprehension of the process of aging in athletes and the ways by which aging can be mitigated in order to increase professional longevity.

Fig. 1. Demonstration of the physical changes related to aging. (Tanaka, 2017)

Fig. 1. Age-related physical changes in Clarence Bass. Reproduced with permission from Mr. Clarence Bass.

Objectives

- (1) Assess exercise, recovery, and aging's impact on athletes, including maintaining performance and well-being.
- (2) Study psychological factors in aging athletes and their effects on well-being and performance.
- (3) Examine physiological influences on athlete aging, particularly hormones and genetics, and their performance effects.
- (4) Review recent medical advancements that may mitigate aging effects on athletes.
- (5) Design a preseason athletic productivity workflow that will help athletes mitigate aging effects. (Table 8)
- (6) Design an anti-aging scorecard for athletes, that can be used on a weekly basis. (Fig. 10)

Methods

The systematic review and meta-analysis were executed according to the recommendations of the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions (version 5.1) In reporting the results, the Primary Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) Statement, and the Meta-analysis of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (MOOSE) guidelines were followed (Moher et al., 2015).

Telomere length was selected as a biological marker to determine the aging effects in this study. VO2 max was also selected for the purpose of cardiovascular and aerobic fitness level determination.

As a result, a meta-analysis was done to test the anti-aging effects of different types of exercises and their benefits on athletes' performance. A case study that tests the effects of hyperbaric oxygen therapy on various body functions and telomere length was also added to the meta-analysis.

The population was grouped based on the following characteristics:

1. Master Athletes: individuals aged over 35 years who are dedicated to training, competition, and sports achievement (Kim et al., 2021)
2. Young Athletes: elite athletes who represented their country in international contests or were competing professionally (Elwood et al., 2021) and below the age range of master athletes.
3. Old Control: Healthy individuals who are sedentary or engaged in recreational activities with the same age range as master athletes.
4. Young control: Healthy individuals who are sedentary or engaged in recreational activities with the same age range as young athletes.

SEARCH METHODS FOR IDENTIFICATION OF STUDIES

Literature was retrieved from PubMed, Web of Science, ClinicalTrials.gov, Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Europe PubMed Central, and Scopus. The search strategy included the following keywords: “elite athletes”, “master athletes”, “anti-aging”, “longevity”, “hormones”, “genetic factors”, “Telomere length”, “Hyperbaric oxygen therapy”, “HBO”, “electronic equipment”, “psychological factors”, “stress”, “exercise”, “training”.

A citation manager was used to save the study data which was collected from the database.

At first, all duplicate studies were deleted. Then, the titles and abstracts of the remaining selected studies were examined in order to determine their eligibility for the systematic review and meta-analysis. In case the information provided in the abstract is not sufficient, the reviewer will read the full text to assess the eligibility.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The inclusion criteria:

1. Study design: In the quantitative analysis, randomized controlled trials (RCT), cohort, and quasi-experimental studies were included. In the qualitative analysis, Systematic reviews and narrative reviews were added.
2. Population: Athletes over 20 years old and at different competitive levels.
3. Intervention: In the quantitative analysis, studies that test TL in athletes were selected. In the qualitative analysis, studies include specific physical or mental training or have a detailed description of the previous training history of participants were selected.
4. Controls: At least one control group was included. However, blank control studies were acceptable.

5. Outcomes: Studies examining changes in elite performance, aerobic capacity, muscle endurance, telomere length, or other performance-related parameters affected by aging were targeted.
6. Studies that were written in English.

Exclusion criteria

1. Study Design: Editorials, commentaries, conference abstracts, letters, and studies lacking original data or empirical research were excluded.
2. Patients: nonhuman, cadaveric, non-athletic populations Studies were excluded. Also, studies that are focused on specific medical conditions or diseases unrelated to aging in athletes.
3. Intervention: Interventions that didn't mention specific physical and mental training or a detailed training or competition history of the participants.
4. Controls: Control groups focused on different interventions or unrelated outcomes that do not follow the primary objectives of the study on anti-aging for athletes.
5. Outcomes: Studies that don't include relevant outcome measures or not assessing the specified interventions.

DATA EXTRACTION

All publications were examined by the author, and data was extracted. In the qualitative analysis section, data extracted include (1) population characteristics (such as number, age, and gender), (2) study information (Intervention), and (3) The main outcome. In the quantitative analysis, data to be extracted are (1) Telomere length, (2) VO2 max, (3) telomere evaluation method, and (4)

population characteristics (Table 2). Finally, all articles were double-checked for correctness.

RISK OF BIAS & QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Included papers were assessed for any bias inclusion. Depending on the following elements: a) the description of the TL evaluation; b) validation and method used to quantify the level of physical activity (e.g., questionnaire); c) equivalent variables (e.g., age and sex); d) researcher blinding for TL analysis; e) sample size, including the calculation; f) statistical analysis. The use of relative TS ratio or absolute measurement was checked each time PCR results were reported. The scores for each item were assigned randomly: zero for not committed, 0.5 for moderately committed, and 1 for entirely committed. The Total rankings varied between 0 to 6, Only researches ranking 3 or more were included.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The changes in TL in the genomic DNA of leukocytes and skeletal muscle from active athletes (endurance sports, sprinting, and powerlifting) and inactive persons (the control group) were examined. “Heterogeneity” refers to the presence of differences between studies for each of the main outcomes studied (high level of exercising vs. sedentary lifestyle). Statistical heterogeneity was measured by Cochran's Q test, with a threshold P-value of 0.1 considered statistically significant, and values > 75% for the inconsistency I² test considered indicative of substantial heterogeneity. This method measures the variety proportion of the results caused by heterogeneity rather than coincidence. The I² values for this approach vary from 0 to 100%, with 0% indicating minimal heterogeneity and 100% indicating very high heterogeneity.

Results

SEARCH RESULTS

721 references were found using the database search. After duplicates were eliminated, there were 698 articles left. Then 610 were eliminated because the examination of the title and abstract suggested the item did not fit the requirements for inclusion. The eligibility of the remaining 88 publications was examined in full text: 49 were found irrelevant to the study focus, 8 studies were discarded because animals were involved, and 4 studies were excluded due to

full-text unavailability. The qualitative analysis comprised twenty-seven studies (n=27), from which nineteen investigations were selected for the quantitative analysis (n = 19). (Fig. 2.)

BASIC CHARACTERISTICS

The meta-analysis included 1469 individuals in 19 studies. Their mean age is 41.8 years and (CI: [35.5, 48.2]). They were categorized as master athletes (n = 486, Male (M) = 358, Female (F) = 128, Mean age = 55.3 [CI] [51.8, 58.8], Old control (n= 394, (M) = 256, (F) = 139, Mean age = 53.9 [CI] [51.5, 56.3], Young athletes (n= 271, (M) = 169, (F) = 102 Mean age = 23.6 [CI] [22.6, 24.5] and Young controls (n= 318, (M) = 201, (F) = 117, Mean age = 23.8 [CI] [22.9, 24.6] (Table 1).

Table 1. Basic characteristics of participants.

Participants	Male	Female	Mean age	Number	CI
Total	984	486	41.8	1469	[35.5, 48.2]
Old control (OC)	256	139	53.9	394	[51.5, 56.3]
Master athletes (MA)	358	128	55.3	486	[51.8, 58.8]
Young athletes (YA)	169	102	23.6	271	[22.6, 24.5]
Young control (YC)	201	117	23.8	318	[22.9, 24.6]

Four studies investigated TL in Sprinters and endurance runners (Aguiar et al., 2021; Aguiar et al., 2022; Nickles et al., 2022; Rosa et al., 2020). Seven studies investigated TL in endurance-trained athletes (Borghini et al., 2015; Denham et al., 2013; Denham et al., 2016; Mathur et al., 2013; Osthus et al., 2012; Rae et al., 2010; La Roca et al., 2010). One study investigated TL in elite master

sprinters (Simoès et al., 2017), one study investigated TL in master rowers (Seki et al., 2023), one study investigated TL with the use of Hyperbaric oxygen therapy (Maroon, 2022), one study investigated TL in female football and handball players (Hagman et al., 2021), one study investigated TL in male football players (Hagman et al., 2020), one study investigated TL in elite swimmers (Nickles et al., 2021), one study investigated TL in powerlifters (Kadi et al., 2008), and one study investigated TL in athletes participating in a variety of activities (running events > 1500 m, triathlons, canoeing 200-1000 m, team sports) (Muniesa et al., 2017). (Table 2)

Telomere length (TL) was measured in peripheral white blood cells (Aguiar et al., 2021; Aguiar et al., 2022; Denham et al., 2013; Denham et al., 2016; Mathur et al., 2013; Rosa et al., 2020; Simoès et al., 2017; Nickles et al., 2021; Nicklas et al., 2022; Maroon, 2022), skeletal muscle (Osthus et al., 2012; Rae et al., 2010), and saliva (Borghini et al., 2015) Buccal cells (Nickles et al., 2021; Nickles et al., 2022). Telomere length was measured using quantitative or real-time polymerase chain reaction (Aguiar et al., 2021; Aguiar et al., 2022; Borghini et al., 2015; Denham et al., 2013; Denham et al., 2016; Osthus et al., 2012; Nickles et al., 2021; Nickles et al., 2022; Maroon, 2022), southern blotting (LaRocca et al., 2010; Rae et al., 2010) or in situ hybridization of fluorescence (Mathur et al., 2013). VO₂ max was measured in 6 studies (Mathur et al., 2013; Østhus et al., 2012; Denham et al., 2016; Seki et al., 2023; Hagman, 2021; LaRocca, 2010) (Table 2).

Table 2. Studies included & findings.

Study	Telomere Length athletes	Telomere length control	VO2 max	Telomere evaluation method	Characteristics (n, sex, age in yrs)
Aguiar et al., 2021	1.1 (0.84)	0.56 (0.56)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	C: 11, M, 45.41 ± 10.34 A: 21, M, 51.62 ± 8.19
Simoes et al., 2017	1.37 (0.9)	0.51 (0.62)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	C: 10, M, 45.4±10.9 A: 11, M, 50.1±9.2
Borghini et al., 2015	1.28 (0.4)	1.02 (0.3)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	C: 42, M32/F10, 45.9±9.5 A: 20, M17/F3, 45.4±9.2
Denham et al., 2013	3.5 (0.68)	3.1 (0.41)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	C: 56, M, 42.8 ± 9.2 A: 67, M, 43.6 ± 9.2
Denham et al., 2016	3.64 (0.06)	3.38(0.06)	C: 43.73 (7.03) A: 58.77 (8.75)	Leukocytes; qPCR	C: 61, M47/F14, 28.7 ± 10.64 A: 61, M46/F15, 33.7 ± 11.03
Mathur et al., 2013	0.89 (0.11)	0.89 (0.12)	C: 33.4 (5.9) A: 43.9 (6.4)	Granulocytes and lymphocytes; fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH)	C: 17, M9/F8, 55 ± 5 A: 15, M10/F5, 54 ± 4
Østhus et al., 2012	MA: 1.12 (0.1) YA: 1.47 (0.2)	OC: 0.92 (0.2) YC: 1.33 (0.1)	MA: 45.4 (6.7) YA: 67 (5.3) OC: 39.4 (39.4) YC: 53.9 (5.5)	Leukocytes; qPCR	OC: 5, M, 69.8 ± 4.4 YC: 5, M, 23.6 ± 2.7 MA: 5, M, 69.2 ± 2.9 YA: 5, M, 24.4 ± 0.6
Rae et al., 2010	10.5 (0.97)	9.94 (1)	—	southern blot analysis	C: 19, M11/F8, 38.7 ± 9.5 A: 18, M12/F6, 42.4 ± 6.9

Study	Telomere Length athletes	Telomere length control	VO2 max	Telomere evaluation method	Characteristics (n, sex, age in yrs)
Seki et al., 2023	8.57 (0.36)	8.56 (0.34)	C: 34.03 (7.9) A: 44.7 (9.9)	RT-PCR, DNA methylation-based estimation of TL (DNAmTL), and DNA methylation-based biomarkers of aging	C: 95, M30/F65, 62 ± 12.3 A: 146, M78/F68, 59 ± 9.7
Maroon, 2022	5.4	—	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	A: 1, M, 81
Nickels et al., 2022	MA: 0.783 (0.135) YA: 0.944 (0.159)	OC: 0.79 (0.11) YC: 0.899 (0.098)	—	leukocytes and buccal cells, qPCR	OC: 12, M5/F7, 49.2 ± 7 YC: 11, M6/F5, 24.1 ± 1.6 MA: 12, M7/F5, 45.5 ± 4.9 YA: 12, M7/F5, 25.6 ± 3.7
Nickels et al, 2021	1.039 (0.136)	1.099 (0.176)	—	leukocytes and buccal cells, qPCR	C: 27, M, 20.3 ± 4.7 A: 29, M, 20.6 ± 1.7
Aguiar, 2022	1.38 (1.05)	0.4 (0.34)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	C: 19, M, 47.6 ± 8.9 A: 52, M, 50 ± 7.3
Hagman, 2021	MA: 3.4 (0.18) YA: 5.67 (0.45)	OC: 3.25 (0.16) YC: 4.59 (0.24)	MA: 30.2 (1.2) YA: 45.3 (1) OC: 23.1 (0.8) YC: 35.7 (0.9)	lymphocytes and MNCs, qPCR	OC: 35, F, 66.1 ± 0.6 YC: 30, F, 24.9 ± 0.4 MA: 35, F, 63.9 ± 0.7 YA: 29, F, 22.5 ± 0.6
Rosa, 2020	1.4 (1)	MC: 0.5 (0.6) YC: 1.9 (1.6)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	MC: 12, M, 45.5 ± 9.8 YC: 17, M, 22.7 ± 3.9 MA: 13, M, 50 ± 8.9

Study	Telomere Length athletes	Telomere length control	VO2 max	Telomere evaluation method	Characteristics (n, sex, age in yrs)
Hagman, 2020	MA: 1.03 (0.054) YA: 1.4 (0.09)	OC: 1.12 (0.036) YC: 1.32 (0.074)	—	FISH & PCR	OC: 35, M, 70.1 ± 0.7 YC: 35, M, 24.3 ± 0.6 MA: 35, M, 71.9 ± 0.5 YA: 35, M, 21.6 ± 0.5
Rosa, 2020*	0.8 (0.5)	MC: 0.5 (0.6) YC: 1.9 (1.6)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	MC: 12, M, 45.5 ± 9.8 YC: 17, M, 22.7 ± 3.9 MA: 18, M, 53 ± 8.2
LaRocca, 2010	MA: 7.8 (0.61) YA: 8.5 (0.93)	MC: 7 (0.52) YC: 8.4 (0.82)	MA: 40.5 (1.7) YA: 55.8 (1.4) OC: 25.9 (1.8) YC: 43.7 (2)	Leukocytes; southern blot analysis	OC: 15, M9/F6, 65 ± 1 YC: 15, M7/F8, 23 ± 1 MA: 17, M11/F6, 62 ± 2 YA: 10, M7/F3, 21 ± 1
Muniesa et al., 2017	0.89 (0.26)	0.78 (0.31)	—	Leukocytes; qPCR	YC: 64, M33/F31, 28.9 ± 6.3 YA: 61, M33/F28, 27.2 ± 4.9
Kadi et al., 2008	11.7 (1.5)	10.5 (0.5)	—	Muscle , TRF (mean)	YC: 7, M, 24.1 ± 2.1 YA: 7, M, 28.5 ± 6.6

Control: C, Athletes: A, Male: M, Female: F, Old Control: OC, Young Control: YC, Master Athletes: MA, Young Athletes: YA, Age-matched Control: MC

Quantitative analysis

The complete outcomes of the 757 athletes (master & young) vs. the 712 controls (old & young) are shown in (Tables 3 & 4).

Table 3. TL comparison

	OC	MA	YA	YC
OC	0.00	-0.322	-0.989	-0.810
MA	0.322	0.00	-0.666	-0.488
YA	0.989	0.666	0.00	0.178
YC	0.810	0.488	-0.178	0.00

Table 4. VO2max comparison

	OC	MA	YA	YC
OC	0.00	16.8	27.1	12.3
MA	-16.8	0.00	10.3	-4.50
YA	-27.1	-10.3	0.00	-14.8
YC	-12.3	4.50	14.8	0.00

The findings of a random-effects meta-analysis were as follows: (1) Young elite athletes and master athletes had a notably longer TL than the young and old control groups respectively, $I^2= 97.7\%$ (95% CI [97.3%, 98.1%]) (Fig. 3 & 4). (2) Young elite athletes and master athletes had notably higher VO2 max values than the young and old control groups respectively, $I^2= 95.2\%$ (95% CI [93.0%, 96.8%]) (Fig. 5 & 6). Heterogeneity was very high because of the different sources of Telomere length detection (blood and buccal cells and skeletal muscle), as well as the inclusion of different exercise routines and sports of the participants, besides the inclusion of studies that deal with master athletes and young athletes together. The mean Telomere length for Master athletes is 0.322 T/S ratio greater than Old Control (95% CI [0.146, 0.498] (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Forest plot comparing TL of master athletes to Controls.

Mean Telomere length for Young athletes is 0.178 T/S ratio greater than Young control (95% CI [-0.0288, 0.385]) (Fig. 4)

Figure 4. Forest plot comparing TL of Young athletes to Controls.

Mean VO2 max for Young athletes is 12.3 ml/min greater than Young control (95% CI [8.56, 16.0]), and Mean VO2 max for Master athletes is 10.3 ml/min greater than Old Control (95% CI [6.85, 13.8]). (Fig. 5 & 6)

Figure 5. Forest plot comparing VO2max of Young athletes to Controls

Figure 6. Forest plot comparing VO2max of Master athletes to Controls

Qualitative analysis

EXERCISE AND RECOVERY

Aerobic & Endurance training:

In trained master athletes, it was evident that aging has a bigger impact on anaerobic vs aerobic power, with a decrease rate of 7-14% each decade in both peak anaerobic and aerobic power, and this rate of decline was not different much between athletic disciplines or sexes (Ganse & Degens, 2021). Moreover, long-term (chronic) aerobic exercise training is seen as an anti-aging factor, which slows the aging process by boosting circulating s-Klotho and decreasing IGF-I levels (Saghiv et al., 2017). Despite the fact that aerobic exercise capacity naturally declines with age, oxygen absorption at the anaerobic threshold stays approximately 3.5-fold higher in elite endurance athletes until 70 years of age when compared to their untrained age-matched individuals (Burtscher, 2012). Kusy & Zieliński, (2015) studied the effects of endurance vs sprint training on aerobic capacity in athletes, the study found that sprint-training athletes (participating in short high-intensity exercise <30 seconds had lower maximal aerobic capacity than endurance-trained athletes (participating in prolonged submaximal exercise) VO_{2max} ~47 vs ~58 $mL \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot min^{-1}$, respectively (Table 5). Other findings of the study will be mentioned in detail in their corresponding sections. According to Borghini et al. (2015), a comparison was made between the telomere length of 42 age- and gender-matched inactive controls (32 males, 45.9 ± 9.5 years) and the telomere length of 20 endurance athletes (17 males, 45.4 ± 9.2 years), those athletes were seasoned runners with an average weekly training distance of 59.4 km and 13.15 years of extreme trail running under their

belts. The 42 inactive individuals (32 men; 45.9 ± 9.5 years old) were selected and matched to the endurance athletes. The criteria for control group selection were not engaging in physical activity and having no history of competitive sports. An analysis was executed using a quantitative real-time PCR under baseline conditions, the halfway point, and the final point of an ultra-distance race. The evaluation happened during the 'Tor des Géants ®' ultra-distance trail race when 12 male athletes (aged 47.2 ± 8.5 years) out of the 20 participants were reevaluated at the halfway point. 11 male athletes (aged 47.1 ± 8.8 years) finished the race and were examined at the halfway point. when comparing the two groups (endurance athletes vs. sedentary controls), a notable difference in TL was found (1.28 ± 0.4 vs. 1.02 ± 0.3 , $P = 0.005$). Also, older endurance runners showed longer TL when compared to the age-matched control group (1.3 ± 0.27 vs. 0.91 ± 0.21 , $P = 0.003$). For athletes competing in the ultra-marathon, TL was considerably lower at the intermediate (0.88 ± 0.36 vs. 1.11 ± 0.34 , $P = 0.002$) and final points than baseline measures (0.86 ± 0.4 vs. 1.11 ± 0.34 , $P = 0.0006$). According to Østhus et al. (2012) cross-sectional study, 20 males were grouped into 10 young (22–27 years old) and 10 old (66–77 years old). A similar increase in Telomere length was found as a consequence of long-term endurance training. Five out of ten young adults and five out of ten older individuals were endurance athletes. The younger athletes were selected from Norway. Based on their involvement in comparable track and field events, the older racers were recruited from a 58-kilometer cross-country ski race. In each age group, the control groups were physically active but not competitive athletes. The exercise frequency of the younger non-athlete group was at least twice a week at a moderate level, while the older non-athlete group was more likely to participate in senior soccer and

dancing. Using a quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction, or "qPCR," the mean telomere length was calculated as the telomere/single copy gene ratio (T/S-ratio). The findings showed that older endurance athletes (T/S ratio 1.1260.1 vs. 0.9260.2, $p = 0.04$) had longer telomere lengths than older individuals with medium exercise levels. There was no difference in TL between Young endurance-trained athletes and young non-athletes (1.4760.2 vs. 1.3360.1, $p = 0.12$). Additionally, VO₂max and T/S ratio showed an important association in this study ($r = 0.78$, $p = 0.02$). Also, Denham et al., (2013) found that ultra-marathon runners had an 11% longer telomere length (T/Sratio) than controls (ultra-marathon runners: 3.560.68, controls: 3.160.41; $b = 0.40$, $SE = 0.10$, $P = 1.461024$) in the age-adjusted analysis as a result of his study of the benefits of ultra-endurance training to mitigate aging, this was demonstrated by examining the leukocyte telomere length (T/S ratio) using real-time quantitative PCR in 67 ultra-marathon runners who had completed at least two ultra-marathons, had an average training distance of 40–100 km/week and had trained for a minimum of two years vs 56 healthy males. On the other hand, Mathur (2013) didn't find any notable difference in lymphocyte (0.97 ± 0.20 vs 1.01 ± 0.18 ; $P = 0.6$) and granulocyte (0.89 ± 0.11 vs 0.89 ± 0.12 ; $P = 0.9$) telomere lengths when he examined 17 marathon runners who practiced long-distance running for at least 5 years, and all ran on an average of more than 21 miles/w vs 15 healthy sedentary controls of the same age respectively.

Resistance Training

According to Suominen et al., (2017), a 20-week randomized controlled trial was conducted to study the effects of high-intensity sprint and strength training on tibial bone structure and strength in middle-aged and older male sprint athletes (>40yrs) following a training program designed in phases, the study included 40 master athletes participants in (EX), and 32 in the control group (CTRL). Strength and sprint training were performed twice a week. The strength training focused mainly on leg muscles, and plyometric exercises were also included. There was no significant effect found on body weight, lean body mass, distal tibia bone traits, or total testosterone. However, EX showed a 2% improvement in the total cross-sectional area of the mineshaft “CSATOT”, cortical CSA “CSACO”, a 2.5% improvement in cortical thickness “ThCO”, 3.2% & 1.8% improvements respectively in the area and density-weighted moments of inertia for the direction of the smallest flexural rigidity (I_{minA} , I_{minD}), a 3.5% improvement in bending and torsional rigidity around the neutral axis of the bone “ I_{polarA} ”, by 0.7% in total bone mineral content “BMCTOT”, and by 2.2% in group \times time interaction at the A-M site “BMCA-M” compared to CTRL (Table 7).

In order to investigate the effects of combined strength and sprint training on the regulation of muscle contraction at the whole-muscle and single-fiber levels, Cristea et al. (2008) conducted another 20-week experimental study on 11 elite master sprinters. The athletes were divided into 7 experimental groups (EX) and 4 control groups (CTRL). The training protocol was $86 \pm 4\%$ for strength training and $83 \pm 6\%$ for sprint training over the 20-week study period. For strength training in EX, the average training hours and frequency across the training period were 2.1 ± 0.2 h and 1.6 ± 0.1 times per week, while for sprint training, they

were 2.1 ± 0.3 h and 1.6 ± 0.1 opportunities each week. The other workouts (skiing, ball games, and aerobic jogging) were done 0.6 ± 0.2 times a week and 0.5 ± 0.2 hours each. The controls kept their run-based training regimens as usual. During unilateral knee extension and knee flexion exercises in EX, the maximal isometric torque increased by 21% ($P < 0.05$) and 40% ($P < 0.01$), respectively. Maximum dynamic strength improved by 27% ($P < 0.001$, $n = 5$) as measured by bilateral concentric 1-RM squat. The mechanical power of the reactive leap test (29%, $P < 0.01$), triple jump (4%, $P < 0.01$), and squat jump (10%, $P < 0.01$) all showed significant increases. There were no notable changes in any of these factors in CTRL. All jump test variables showed greater increases for the EX group than for the CTRL group when comparing the percentage changes across the intervention period ($P < 0.05$ – 0.01). In EX, there was an 8% increase ($P < 0.05$) in the propulsive phase of the contact, while the average resultant force of the braking phase of contact remained the same (2%, $P = 0.18$). During the propulsive phase, the ground contact periods decreased by 5% ($P < 0.05$) and the braking phase by 9% ($P < 0.01$), respectively. The rate of resultant force development (RFD) increased as a result of these modifications in both the propulsive (14%, $P < 0.05$) and braking (12%, $P < 0.05$) phases. Also, the 60-meter sprint time decreased from 8.69 ± 0.30 to 8.52 ± 0.29 s (2%, $P < 0.01$), and the maximal 10-meter running speed increased from 7.47 ± 0.28 to 7.74 ± 0.31 m s⁻¹ (4%, $P < 0.01$). The maximum speed phase's stride length increased from 1.79 ± 0.06 to 1.85 ± 0.08 m (3%, $P < 0.05$), although the stride rate (from 4.19 ± 0.10 to 4.22 ± 0.13 Hz) did not significantly change. There were no discernible changes in CTRL. (Table 7)

Table 5. Skeletal muscle adaptations towards concurrent, strength, and endurance training. (Coffey & Hawley, 2007)

Author	WK	Training	Concurrent Training Interference?
Izquierdo et al. (2005)	16	(S) 2 d/wk (E) 2 d/wk (C) 1 x S + 1 x E once weekly	Yes – lower leg strength development
Glowacki et al. (2004)	12	(S) 2-3 x wk (E) 2-3 x wk (C) 5 x wk	Yes – reduced increase of maximum oxygen consumption in C vs. E
Häkkinen et al. (2003)	21	(S) 2 d/wk (C) 2 x S + 2 x E	Yes – impaired explosive strength development
Balabinis et al. (2003)	7	(S) 4 d/wk (E) 4 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / same day	No
Millet et al. (2002)	14	(E) triathlon precondition phase (C) E + S-2 x wk	No
McCarthy et al. (2002)	10	(S) 3 d/wk (E) 3 d/wk (C) combined S + E in same session	No
Bell et al. (2000)	12	(S) 3 d/wk (E) 3 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / alternate day	Yes - impaired strength gains in C compared with S
Horne et al. (1997)	12	(S) 3 d/wk (E) 3 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / alternate day	Yes - impaired strength gains in C compared with S
Kraemer et al. (1995)	12	(S) 4 d/wk (E) 4 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / same day	Yes - impaired strength gains in C compared with S
McCarthy et al. (1995)	10	(S) 3 d/wk (E) 3 d/wk (C) combined S + E in same session	No
Hennessy & Watson (1994)	8	(S) 3 d/wk (E) 4 d/wk(C) random S+E combined & separate 5 d/wk	Yes – impaired strength gains in C compared with S
Nelson et al. (1990)	20	(S) 4 d/wk (E) 4 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / same day	Yes – reduced increase of maximum oxygen consumption in C vs. E
Hunter et al. (1987)	12	(S) 4 d/wk (E) 4 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / same day	Yes – reduced vertical jump in C compared with S
Dudley & Djamil (1985)	7	(S) 3 x wk (E) 3 x wk (C) S + E regimens / alternate day	Yes – reduced maximum torque at high velocities in C vs. S
Hickson (1980)	10	(S) 5 d/wk (E) 6 d/wk (C) S + E regimens / same day	Yes – impaired strength gains in C compared with S group

S, strength training; E endurance training; C, concurrent strength and endurance training

A study by Kadi et al., (2008) made a comparison between the telomere lengths of seven powerlifters (PL; N = 7) who had been training for 8 ± 3 years and seven healthy, active people (C; N = 7) who had never been engaged in strength training. The study of skeletal muscle utilized a southern blot methodology, tissue biopsies were taken from the "Vastus Lateralis" and mean as well as minimum telomeric restriction fragments (TRF) (Telomere Length) were measured. In PL, no abnormal telomere shortening was detected. On the other hand, it was observed that the lowest TRF length ($P = 0.09$) and mean ($P = 0.07$) TRF length in PL tended to be higher than in C whereby individual records for squat and deadlift revealed a negative correlation ($r = -0.86$; $P = 0.01$) with the minimum TRF length in PL ($r = -0.88$; $P = 0.01$). These results indicate that a typical shortening of the length of telomeres in skeletal muscle is not associated with long-term exercise. Even if muscle telomere length remains within the physiologically normal range for PL, skeletal muscle TRF is shortened by increased strain in the muscles.

Finally, Coffey & Hawley (2007), Studied the molecular basis of adaptive training and made a table that summarises skeletal muscle effects to concurrent, strength endurance training. (Table 5).

Anaerobic training

As previously mentioned, Kusy & Zieliński, (2015) studied the effects of endurance vs sprint training on aerobic capacity in athletes. During the investigation of anaerobic training, it was found that the Sprint group showed a lower rate of decline in Maximal Aerobic Capacity: VO_{2max} , and Sub-maximal Aerobic Capacity: VO_{2GET} than the endurance group with a value of VO_{2max} :

0.31 vs 0.46 mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹ per year & VO₂GET: 0.38 vs 0.56 mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹ per year. (Table 7)

Rosa et al. (2020) conducted a study comparing the redox balance, cytokine levels, and aging biomarkers of master sprinters, endurance athletes, and young and middle-aged controls. Besides the untrained youth (YC, 22.7 ± 3.9 yrs; n = 17) and age-matched controls (MC, 45.5 ± 9.8 yrs; n = 12), the participants included male master sprinters (SA, 50 ± 8.9 yrs; n = 13) and endurance runners (EA, 53 ± 8.2 yrs; n = 18), who had a long athletic experience of about 25 years of practice. All of the subjects' anamnesis, anthropometrics, aging biomarkers, inflammatory state, and oxidative stress indicators were examined. Outcomes MC showed a greater pro-oxidant activity (higher protein carbonyl; isoprostanes and 8-OHdG) than the other groups (p < 0.05). Also, SA had a greater antioxidant capacity than both MC and EA, although the availability of nitrite/nitrate (NO_x) was shown to be higher in EA and lower in MC (p < 0.05). Compared to MC (increased IL-10 and dropped IL-6, sIL-6R, and sTNF-RI), both athlete groups had better anti-inflammatory status; however, compared to YC (increased TNF-α, sTNF-RI, and sIL-6R) (p < 0.05). In MC, there was an increase in FGF-23 (p < 0.05) and a decrease in irisin and klotho levels, along with a shorter telomere length. When comparing EA to SA and YC, irisin levels were lower and ADMA levels were greater in MC and SA (p < 0.05).

In a study conducted by Herbert et al., (2017) to test the effect of High-Intensity Interval Training (HIIT) on muscle power and free testosterone levels in male master athletes, Seventeen male master athletes (60 ± 5 years) completed the intervention, which comprised nine HIIT sessions over six weeks. HIIT sessions involved six 30-s sprints at 40% Peak Power Output (PPO), combined with 3 min

active recovery. Absolute PPO (799 ± 205 W and 865 ± 211 W) and relative PPO (10.2 ± 2.0 W/kg and 11.0 ± 2.2 W/kg) increased from pre- to post-HIIT respectively ($P < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 0.32-0.38$). (Table 7)

On the other hand, Nickels et al., (2021) conducted a study on TL in Elite swimmers (41% sprint ≤ 100 m), 39% middle ($\leq 200-800$ m), and 20% long (≥ 800 m)) that showed an unfavorable effect of high-level swimming training and/or competition on telomere length and subsequent biological aging, Specially in females.

Recovery

Aging can affect the recovery kinetics of athletes, potentially impacting their performance (Borges et al., 2016). Easthope et al. (2010) conducted a study to analyze recovery rates in ultra-endurance athletes. The study included 13 master runners (45.9 ± 5.9 years) and 10 younger runners (30.5 ± 7.0 years) after a 55 km trail running race. The assessment of muscle strength and hematological biomarkers of muscle damage, namely lactate dehydrogenase and creatine kinase, was conducted 72 hours after the event to investigate the level of exhaustion and the extent of recovery from the trail run. The finding revealed that older athletes and master athletes both felt similar degrees of exhaustion. Also, there were no large variations in the recovery rates of cycling efficiency and biochemical indicators of muscle damage between the two age groups. However, ultra-endurance master athletes needed a lot longer time for their muscle function to return to normal. The younger ultra-endurance group's MVC, muscle twitch, and M-wave characteristics all returned to baseline values 24 hours following their 55-kilometer trail run. The muscle function of the master ultra-endurance group was restored to baseline levels 48 hours following the 55-kilometer trail run,

whereas the M-wave and muscular twitch properties did not return to baseline levels during the 72-hour recovery period. These results suggest that master athletes recover more slowly from a stimulus that results in severe muscle damage, even though the degree of tiredness appears to be age-independent. Furthermore, compared to younger athletes, it seems that neuromuscular function in the master athlete group is still much worse. (Table 7)

On the other hand, Fell et al. (2008), found that there was no difference in the recovery of time trial performance between nine master cyclists (aged 45 ± 6 years) and nine younger cyclists (aged 24 ± 5 years). For three days, both groups of riders executed three 30-minute cycling time trials aimed at causing muscular exhaustion. The researchers found that older cyclists showed a notable difference in perceived measures of exhaustion, recuperation, and muscular soreness between the first and third-time trial, even though neither group's performance decreased across the three 30-minute time trials. The younger group, in contrast, did not exhibit any notable change in the same perceptual measures between the first and third trials. Additionally, an important observation between the groups concerning the shift in the subjective assessment of muscle pain from the initial to the third time trial was made, indicating modified frequencies of muscle discomfort related to aging. Despite the finding in the Fell et al. (2008) study that suggests older athletes can recover from exhaustion as quickly as younger athletes, according to the same study, master athletes may feel it takes them longer to recover fully from a previous workout.

In the field of recovery method selection, Bezuglov et al., (2021) conducted a study about the actual recovery techniques that Athletes frequently use. The study used Google Forms to gather data from elite endurance track and field

athletes (n = 153, 61.4% men, 38.6% women; average age: 22.7 ± 4.6 years) on their recovery strategies. Sauna bathing (96.7%), massage (86.9%), midday naps (81.0%), and extended sleep (at least nine hours) (61.4%) were the most popular recovery techniques. Successful recovery techniques, such as compression garments and immersion in cold water, were not regularly used (15.0% and 7.8%, respectively) (Table 5). Generally, recovery techniques were applied more frequently when track and field competitors were at higher ranks. Russian endurance track and field competitors most frequently used massage and sauna baths as post-exercise recovery techniques. They were typically employed in association with a full night's sleep and a quick midday nap. Elite-level athletes were more likely to use sauna bathing, massage, long night sleep, and midday naps as recovery techniques than they were to use cold water immersion or compression garments. Still, all of these techniques were commonly employed by elite-level athletes. (Bezuglov et al., 2021) (Figure 7)

Fig. 7. Recovery procedure application based on athlete level. (Bezuglov et al., 2021)

Also, Cullen et al., (2021) studied various recovery modalities, including Compression Garments and Devices, Cryotherapy, Neuromuscular Electric Stimulation (NMES), Localized Percussive Therapy (PT), Vibratory Therapy (VT), and Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBO). A detailed description and how to use these modalities was not included in the study however, it provided valuable insights into the benefits and limitations of using them. (HBO will be discussed in the medical advances section).

Compression Garments and Devices: According to Cullen et al., (2021) the benefit of compression garments on specific physiological biomarkers is not clear. Also, they didn't prove to be harmful. They didn't show important proof concerning the reduction in blood lactate levels, management of body temperature, or direct improvement of athletic performance. On the other hand, they showed good effects on muscle damage perceptions, they also helped endurance and lowered the risks of overuse injuries. Custom garments, which are garments specially made for athletes using 3D scans, proved to be reliable in enhancing strength, muscle recovery, and power much more than standard garments. **Cryotherapy:** the common cryotherapy methods which include cold water immersion (CWI) and whole-body cryotherapy (WBC), are used for recovery aiming to reduce inflammation and muscle soreness, and speed up metabolite removal. However, studies that support their effectiveness are not certain. There are concerns about the safety of the use of WBC. There are risks that are involved while using WBC like frostbite, burns, eye injuries, and potential neurological or cardiovascular complications in severe cases. Also, specific medical conditions are contraindicated for WBC, which requires caution in its use. Studies on cryotherapy's effect on recovery markers showed different results. Some studies

showed decreased muscle soreness and certain inflammatory markers, but other studies found no improvements, like creatine kinase (CK) levels (Cullen et al., 2021). **(NMES)**: NMES showed an effect in improving blood lactate levels and perceptions of pain, but no solid evidence regarding its effectiveness in recovery was found. Studies highlighted the importance of NMES intensity but lacked consistent evidence to recommend its use for recovery (Cullen et al., 2021). **(PT) & (VT)**: Percussive devices that combine compression and vibration, claimed benefits like improving blood flow and reducing muscle soreness. Research showed some promising results but lacked conclusive evidence, which requires more studies to define optimal treatment protocols and safety precautions. (Cullen et al., 2021)

Table 6. Recommendation and precautions of various recovery modalities. (Cullen et al., 2021)

Modality	Evidence	Precautions	Recommendation
Compression			
Garments	Level I	No known harm	Benefit
Device	Level IV	No known harm	Possible benefit
Cryotherapy			
CWI	Level I, III	Extensive	Benefit
PBC	Level IV	Extensive	Possible benefit
WBC	Levels II, III	Extensive (see section)	Possible benefit
Hyperbaric O ²			
Hyperbaric O ²	Level II, III	Extensive (see section)	Possible benefit
NMES			
NMES	Level I, III	Rhabdomyolysis, muscle fatigue	No benefit
Percussive/vibration			
PT	N/a		
PT	Level II	Possibly underlying blood disorders	Not enough data
VT	Level I	None at this time	Benefit

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS

According to Mehrosfar et al., (2020), The study revealed that a number of factors can have an impact on the psychological state of elite athletes. The most significant of these factors is “Competitive Stress,” which involves the pressure to perform better in competitions and keep on high-level performance. Such kind of stress could be physical and mental; which encompasses the strain involved when one is preparing to participate or engaging in a competition, and how they handle its results. Athletes are subject to numerous psychological stressors, such as intense training atmospheres, varying coaching moods which at times can be stressful, pressing family life, and the disparities between athletes’ sporting lifestyles against their non-sport lifestyles. Besides, Athletes also encounter unrealistic demands from different components of the society like media houses, fans, and professionals.

Organizations increasing the burden on athletes’ stress levels. After competitions, the outcome of performance can be a source of stress for athletes. This entails managing expectations, dealing with the negative outcomes of failed events, and coping while under pressure as athletes fight to preserve their performance or improve it. Chronic stress poses a great danger to an athlete’s physical and mental health if unaddressed, it will ultimately result in burnout; injury; depression; anxiety, impaired metabolism, and compromised immune function. Mehrosfar et al. (2020) also reported that long-term exposure to stressors can result in a decrease in the activity of telomerase(TA), an enzyme responsible for renewing and lengthening telomeres. This decrease in TA leads to faster shortening of telomeres and is associated with shorter TL. Continuous exposure to stressors can promote the process of telomere attrition, which will result in a shortened TL.

This shortening of telomeres represents a surrogate for the accelerated aging process within cells and is associated with various health risks. Finally, Mehrsafari et al., (2020) conducted a study on the impact of various psycho-behavioral interventions such as Mindfulness, Yoga practices Meditation Cognitive Behaviour Intervention (CBI), and Integrated Health Promotion Programmes in TA TL. There exists substantial evidence that engaging oneself in mindful-based interventions may indeed reduce the stress effects and improve cellular health. The psycho-behavioral approaches with good potential to impact TL and TA included cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). Preliminary results show that these interventions may positively affect cellular aging markers. Still, further research is needed on that topic. Integrated Health Promotion Programs: Interventions with such components as low-calorie foods, moderate aerobic exercise, psychobehavioral practices, and group support sessions demonstrated potential results. For instance, an integrative health promotion intervention revealed a greater TA after three months of the program, which is consistent with reduced psychological distress. (Mehrsafari et al., 2020)

Psychological stress can lead to increased oxidative stress, which, although conditioned athletes may develop tolerance to, can still have detrimental effects on the body (Stone et al., 2019). Aguiar et al. (2021) conducted a study to examine the impact of oxidative stress and body fat on telomere length (Table 2). The participants included 21 elite master athletes who had trained for 26.4 ± 11.9 years, 9.2 ± 3.9 hours per week, and 4.8 ± 3.5 competitions annually, as well as 11 untrained, age-matched controls. Compared to untrained controls, the elite master athletes had a longer Leukocyte TL; Cohen's $d = 0.849$ suggests a

substantial effect size. Compared to the untrained control group (26.03 64.29% body fat; 1.29 60.59 conicity index; $p < 0.05$), the top master athletes' relative body fat and conicity index were considerably lower (12.21 64.14% body fat; 1.15 60.09 conicity index). In comparison to master athletes, the untrained control had lower oxidative stress parameters: catalase activity (CAT activity), superoxide dismutase (SOD), lipid peroxidation (TBARS), The redox balance (SOD/TBARS, and CAT/TBARS ratios), according to the examination of pro-oxidant and antioxidant parameters. There was no difference in oxidative damage (TBARS) or superoxide dismutase activity across the groups.

PHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS

Kusy & Zieliński, (2015) mentioned that both endurance and sprint-trained athletes have Stable insulin sensitivity and β -cell function, Similar low body fat percentage in older sprinters and endurance athletes, but Higher lean body mass in aging sprinters indicating greater muscle mass, Greater bone mineral density, & higher fasting glucose in sprinters vs. endurance group (0.12 and 0.08 mmol·L⁻¹, respectively), Sprinters also outperformed endurance runners in neuromuscular tests, older endurance athletes performed below average in countermovement jump (Table 5). Also, a comparison was conducted by Aguiar et al., (2022) between age-matched non-athletes ($n = 19$; aged 47.3 ± 8.9 years) and highly trained male master athletes ($n = 52$; aged 49.9 ± 7.2 years) in terms of insulin, SIRT1, and telomere length (Table 2). All of the data for this cross-sectional study were gathered in a single visit. Using commercial kits, whole blood insulin levels and SIRT1 were measured after an overnight fast. Using qPCR studies, the relative telomere length of leukocytes was ascertained. Compared to age-matched non-athletes, master athletes exhibited longer telomere length,

lower insulin, and increased SIRT1 ($p < 0.05$ for all). SIRT1 and insulin had an inverse relationship ($r = -0.38$; $p = 0.001$). While there was no correlation between telomere length and insulin ($r = 0.03$; $p = 0.87$), there was a positive correlation between telomere length and SIRT1 ($r = 0.65$; $p = 0.001$).

Sellami et al., (2019) investigated the relationship between aging, exercise, and various hormones critical to metabolic functions, summarizing the effects of different exercise modalities on hormones associated with glucose regulation and growth, namely insulin, IGF-1, growth hormone, glucagon, cortisol, and catecholamines as follows: 1. **Insulin**: Aging leads to increased fasting insulin and decreased insulin sensitivity. Long-term endurance training (e.g., six to twelve months) seems effective in reducing fasting insulin, while short-term programs (e.g., two weeks) may not show immediate changes. Sprint training and resistance training also show promising results. Short sprint training might be able to decrease fasting insulin in the older participants thus improving their levels of this hormone. 2. **IGF-1**: A decrease in IGF-1 associated with aging is referred to as 'somatopause.' This may be one of the causes for declining anabolic hormones thus causing athletes to age. In older individuals, the results of endurance training for several months have been inconsistent. The data seems to indicate that sprint training, even though it is of a shorter-term nature appears capable of increasing IGF-1 and particularly so in subjects who do not exercise. However, the impact may be different for inactive versus trained people. The effects of resistance training are also quite variable. Some studies recorded enhanced circulating IGF-1 in older individuals as a result of resistance training, while others recorded reduced systemic IGF-1 levels despite increased lean mass

that resulted from such exercises. Literature has shown that types of physical activities like sprint, resistance, and combined training have the potential to delay the age-related reduction in IGF-1. Despite this, the validity of such influence and whether it is constant or not can vary based on different training modalities and older populations. 3. **Growth Hormone (GH)**: Decreased GH secretion in older adults by age is also known as somatopause, which is associated with reduced muscle mass and vitality. While there is limited research on the effects of endurance and resistance training in older people, it appears that combined sprint and resistance training raises the GH level even in younger adults.

4. **Glucagon**: The pancreas alpha cells produce Glucagon, which is a hormone that plays an important role in elevating blood glucose levels. It opposes the function of insulin by stimulating the release of stored glucose and fatty acids, acting as the main hormone associated with catabolic features. One study has shown that glucagon levels are increased in untrained subjects, but otherwise, there is a lack of research on the effects of exercise on elderly individuals.

5. **Cortisol**: Cortisol is a glucocorticoid hormone that is secreted by adrenal glands. It is the major stress hormone, and it is also involved in the regulation of many physiological functions such as metabolism, immune response, and stress adaptation. High basal cortisol levels are linked with aging. The influence of exercise on cortisol is varied ranging from no significant change with endurance or resistance training to acute responses following specific exercises, like combined sprint and resistance training in middle-aged men that showed post-training an elevation at upload super-maximal sprint.

6. **Catecholamines**: Catecholamines, encompassing hormones such as adrenaline epinephrine and noradrenaline norepinephrine, have a vital role in the

body's response to stress, and also have a vital role in the proper regulation of heart rate, blood pressure, and metabolism. There is limited information on the impact of exercise on older individuals with catecholamines. So far, studies conducted on young subjects suggest that different types and intensities of exercise may have an effect on catecholamine levels but the specific impact in older adults has not been clarified (Sellami et al., 2019). According to Barbosa et al., (2021), Low-grade systemic inflammation and reduced levels of anabolic hormones are commonly associated with aging. That's why Barbosa et al., (2021), conducted a study to assess the association between inflammatory biomarkers and testosterone levels in male master athletes vs. non-athletes. 70 elite power and endurance master athletes (EMA) 51.3 ± 8.0 years old, 32 young individuals (YC; 23.7 ± 3.9 years old), and 24 untrained (MAC; 47.2 ± 8.0 years old) acted as controls, with their venous blood samples drawn for measurement of circulating hormones such as luteinizing hormone[LH]total testosterone estradiol sex hormone binding globulin [SHBG], and free androgen index [FAI] and inflammatory parameters (IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-10). Regarding the signs of an anti-inflammatory state, EMA was better than MAC (greater IL-10, IL-10/IL-6 ratio, and lower IL-6) but YC entailed better results in comparison to EMA ((lower TNF- α) ($p < 0.05$). In comparison to the YC and EMA groups, the MAC group exhibited lower testosterone levels ($p < 0.05$), as well as lower estradiol levels and testosterone/LH ratio ($p < 0.05$) than the YC group. Testosterone had a negative correlation with age and pro-inflammatory parameters in the control groups (MAC, YC) but presented positive correlations to anti-inflammatory markers. (Barbosa et al., 2021) When Seki et al. (2023) examined the connections between physiological functions, maximal oxygen uptake (VO₂max), vertical jump, working

memory, telomere length (TL) assessed by RT-PCR, DNA methylation-based estimation of TL (DNAmTL), and DNA methylation-based biomarkers of aging of master rowers, who participated in the 2019 Masters World Rowing Championships in Venice (Age: 59 ± 9.7 yrs, N = 146) and resting subjects (Age: 62 ± 12.3). The TL was found to have a negative correlation with age. They could not detect any linkage between telomere length and VO₂ max, vertical jump, and working memory via the RT-PCR method.

While the results of these physiological tests suggested an association with DNAmTL. The estimated TL based on the two techniques had a negative correlation with DNAmGrimAge and DNAmPheno-Age acceleration. Contrary to that, exercising and physiological fitness generally seem not to have any notable positive impact on the process of shortening telomeres; however, it should be noted there is an established correlation between telomere length with DNA methylation levels. Coffey & Hawley (2007), Discussed the Genetic and molecular responses exercise, they outlined how endurance as well as resistance training affects skeletal muscle at genetic and cellular levels. They stated that “Endurance training”:

1. Significantly enhances mitochondrial content through the modulation of several transcription factors such as peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha (PGC-1 α), nuclear respiratory factors one and two NRF- I / II And mitochondria Transcription factor A (Tfam);
2. This results in increased activity of genes that participate in carbohydrate and fat metabolism which further contributes to the enhanced endurance capacity,
3. Activates PGC-1 α , which emerges as a central regulator, enhancing mitochondrial biogenesis and lipid metabolism through its association with transcription factors like Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptors (PPARs), while “Resistance

training”: Induces expression of muscle atrophy-related genes, including Muscle Atrophy F-box (MAFBx) and Muscle RING Finger protein (MuRF); however chronic resistance training reduces the production of these genes which potentially can save muscles. **Myostatin Expression:** Resistance Exercise generally decreases myostatin expression but there are cases where it does not happen depending on exercise type, duration, and individual differences.

Interaction of Hypertrophy and Atrophy Pathways: It has been demonstrated that exercise through skeletal muscle contraction can influence regulators of both hypertrophy and atrophy pathways in the muscles with the amount, time or duration of exercise influencing how these responses are shaped. Coffey & Hawley, (2007) Also discussed the Genetic and Molecular Responses to concurrent training — which is the integration of both endurance (aerobic) and resistance (strength or hypertrophic) training within a periodized training plan — as follows:

1. The study suggests that endurance exercise results in Eukaryotic Elongation Factor 2 (eEF2) phosphorylation and subsequent inhibition of translation elongation, thereby reducing the synthesis of proteins. On the other hand, resistance training could reduce eEF2 phosphorylation and thereby improve protein synthesis as well as hypertrophy.
2. Forkhead box O transcription factors (FoxO) that are implicated in the regulation of mRNA abundance for processes such as mitochondrial biogenesis and myofibrillar protein degradation. Activation of Protein Kinase B (AKT) phosphorylates FoxO, affecting hypertrophy and mitochondrial biogenesis-related gene expression. Endurance exercise could elevate the expression of PGC-1 α gene, but it may also raise ubiquitin gene expression influencing protein degradation.

3. based on these results, a study presents “master-switch” hypothesis that Adenosine Monophosphate-activated Protein Kinase (AMPK) and AKT pathways oppose to one another under different exercise stimuli. On the other hand, low-frequency endurance-like stimulation might activate AMPK which will promote mitochondrial adaptation while high-frequency resistance-like stimulations could activate AKT promoting hypertrophy signaling. 4. Researchers propose that AMPK and AKT signaling pathways could guide skeletal muscle adaptation to an aerobic or hypertrophic phenotype, which would promote the specificity of training adaptations. (Table 5)

RECENT MEDICAL ADVANCES

According to Oyaizu et al., (2018), there is potential in HBOT to allow for quicker phases of muscle healing and potentially improve muscular strength as well as help to speed the recovery process with injuries related to soft tissue. Besides its influence on cellular recovery and tissue repair, it can ameliorate the post-exercise recuperation period as well. Maroon, (2022), conducted a research that showed the practice of sixty daily HBO₂ therapy using a routine consisting of sixty daily sessions (five days/week) in a class A multi-place chamber (Fink Engineering, Australia). The session duration was 2 hours, one hour at two ATA of pressure (101 kPa) and it also took another twenty minutes to be compressed and decompressed at the rate of one meter per minute each. 100% oxygen was delivered in an intermittent manner, with the use of a ResMed Quattro FX NV mask that blew continuously 20–35 L per minute alternated by five minutes of breathing air. The subject engaged himself in a cognitive training program during the period he breathed pure oxygen at the target pressure for twenty (20) minutes—in every session. The neurocognitive scores revealed an improvement in all the

other aspects of cognitive function as well as a global cognitive function which ranged from 3.1% to 3.8%. Perfusion MRI showed enhancement of the cerebral perfusion in several memory, coordination, and functioning-related areas varying from 43.3% to 52%. 8.79-16.12% increasing enhancement in cerebral perfusion SPECT scans was found on both the subcallosal area and lingual gyrus, as well as the temporal pole & entorhinal cortex that supports memory. Also, notable increases in fractional anisotropy were recorded by MRI-DTI in several white matter regions, including the tapetum (22.06%), the fornix (16.85%), and the corpus callosum (9%). 7–15% improvements were also recorded in anaerobic threshold, exercise endurance, muscle strength, gait speed, and grip strength. TL was doubled after 40 sessions and clusters of inflammatory proteins decreased and stayed low until the 60th session. More randomized clinical trials with broader sample sizes and similar biomarkers should be conducted to confirm the results, and determine how soon these benefits will prevail (Maroon, 2022). However, according to Cullen et al., (2021), Limited research in the HBOT field indicated promising results regarding enhancing recovery and mitigating markers of muscle damage; however, safety concerns were mentioned such as oxygen toxicity and barotrauma. This is why, more rigorous human studies are required (Cullen et al., 2021).

The literature does not establish a direct link between Electronic equipment and anti-aging. For instance, the integration of electronic equipment especially smartwatches and fitness trackers emerges as a boon in monitoring training load, prevention of injury, and enhancing athlete health (Hamstra-Wright et al., 2021). These tools not only gather useful athlete data but also contribute to sports rehabilitation and injury prevention methods (Moaveninejad & Janes, 2023) that

enable regaining elite performance as well as the proper maintenance of a career in several different professional sport types.

The introduction of regenerative medicine in wound healing and cutaneous injuries can be beneficial to the athlete since aging or elderly individuals have lower capacity for healing (Pang et al., 2017; Gurtner & Chapman, 2016). Regenerative medicine—with therapies such as stem cell treatments and platelet-rich plasma injections—shows potential for musculoskeletal injuries and age-related tissue deterioration (Sepúlveda et al., 2015). These therapeutic procedures, when applied during injuries in skeletal muscles can stimulate myofiber regeneration and prevent scarring, which is of great importance to aging athletes (Kang & Zheng, 2013). Its use in sports medicine involves promoting tissue repair and functional recovery, particularly with chronic tendinopathies and recalcitrant conditions (Sepúlveda et al., 2015; Finnoff et al., 2021). Nevertheless, careful and responsible application coupled with adherence to guidelines will necessarily result in positive outcomes (Ferrari, 2021; Christakou & Lavallee, 2009).

Table 7. Cohort studies were included in the qualitative analysis.

Ref	Population & Characteristics (Number, age (yrs))	Intervention	outcomes
Coffey & Hawley, 2007	6 Endurance Trained (ET) = 28.7 ± 6.1 7 Strength Trained (ST) = 30.7 ± 8.4	measuring Signal and mRNA responses of athletes to habitual and unfamiliar exercises	genetic predisposition influence the molecular response to exercise

Ref	Population & Characteristics (Number, age (yrs))	Intervention	outcomes
Cristea et al., 2008	7 Experimental Group (EX) = 66±3 4 Control Group (CTRL) = 71±5	EX underwent a 20-week program combining sprint training with heavy and explosive strength exercises, while CTRL continued their usual run-based training	↑ Maximal isometric, dynamic leg strength, explosive jump performance, and force production in running in the EX group. Hypertrophic muscular adaptations observed primarily in Ila fibers.
Herbert, et al., (2017)	17 male masters' athletes 60 ± 5	Six-week low-volume High-Intensity Interval Training (HIIT)	Increased Absolute and Relative PPO post-HIIT ($P < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 0.32-0.38$) small increase in free testosterone (7.0 ± 1.2 ng/dL to 7.5 ± 1.1 ng/dL pre- to post-HIIT ($P = 0.050$, Cohen's $d = 0.40$))
Suominen et al., (2017)	72, M, (40–85yrs) EX= 40 CTRL= 32	EX: 20-week program combining heavy and explosive strength exercises with sprint training	No effects on distal tibia bone traits. Increase in cortical thickness.

Ref	Population & Characteristics (Number, age (yrs))	Intervention	outcomes
Bezuglov et al., 2021	Elite endurance track and field athletes ($n = 153$, 61.4% men, 38.6% women; average age: 22.7 ± 4.6 years)	Used recover methods questionnaire	sauna bathing (96.7%) massage (86.9%) daytime nap (81.0%) night sleep 61.4% CWI 15%, compression garments 7.8%
Easthope et al. (2010)	13 master runners (45.9 ± 5.9 years) and 10 younger runners (30.5 ± 7.0 years)	Pre, post 1, 24, 48 and 72 h measurements of muscle strength and hematological biomarkers of muscle damage related to a 55 km trial running race.	CK and LDH elevated, reductions in MVC values (-32 vs. -40% in young and master, $P < 0.01$), drops in EMG, increases in contraction time and declines in peak twitch values. Decline in locomotion efficiency (-4.6 vs. -6.3% in young and master, $P < 0.05$). Masters displayed equal levels of exhaustion and muscular injury as younger people, but their recovery was slower.

Ref	Population & Characteristics (Number, age (yrs))	Intervention	outcomes
Kusy & Zieliński, (2013)	52 sprint-trained track and field athletes (SP): 48.7 ± 19.8 85 endurance runners (ER): 46.0 ± 14.8 55 untrained individuals (UT): 45.8 ± 14.6	Comparison of different athlete groups with untrained individuals	BMI: ER < SP & UT. VO2max: ER > SP > UT total Hb and HCT: ER highest. TCh : UT > SP, ER HDL-c: SP < ER & UT. TG: SP < ER & UT. LDL-c levels & LDL/HDL ratios: no difference. Average fasting glucose : SP highest, no difference between ER and UT. IFG was found in 24 (46.2%) of the SP athletes, 18 (21.2%) of the ER athletes, and 11 (20.0%) of the UT competitors. HOMA-%S was lowest in the UT group, significantly higher in the SP group and highest in the ER group

Ref	Population & Characteristics (Number, age (yrs))	Intervention	outcomes
Fell et al., (2008)	Nine young (Y) (24+/-5 years) and 9 old (V) (45+/-6 years) cyclists	Perceptions of muscle soreness (SOR), fatigue, and recovery recorded in (Y) and V (>35 years) well-trained cyclists after 3 days of repeated cycling time trials	No difference in either group's performance at the 30-min cycling time trials (TT30) between T1 and T3. In the V group, SOR, weariness, and recovery changed dramatically over the course of three days, but not in the Y group. Between T1 and T3, the V group's SOR changed by a substantial amount more than that of the Y group (22+/-14 mm vs. 9+/-12 mm, respectively; P=0.04).

Discussion

In this study, the effects of aging on athletes' performance and well-being were examined, considering various aspects that encompass exercise, recovery, physiological changes, and the integration of cutting-edge medical advancements.

The meta-analysis's primary finding demonstrated that Master & elite athletes have longer TL than their corresponding age-matched controls. However, when we compare the TL of master athletes (MA) to Young control (YC), we will find that YC has longer telomere length than MA despite living a sedentary lifestyle. (Fig. 8)

Figure 8. Forest plot comparing TL of Young controls to MA

It is not possible to completely stop or reverse the aging effect on athletes, but it can be reduced. The key to mitigating aging effects is consistency. According to a study conducted by Saßenroth et al. in 2015, engaging in physical exercise consistently for at least ten years can have a long-lasting impact on telomere length.

Psychological aspects of aging among athletes include numerous stressors — from physical causes such as overtraining and injuries to situational and interpersonal origins related to competitive pressure or team dynamics (Nikolaidis et al. 2015; Medic et al., 2013; Simpson et al., 2023). Mehrsavar et al., (2020) focused on how the effects of lifestyle, stress, psychological issues, and physical exercise have a direct or indirect role regarding cellular aging—namely concerning telomere length TL which is considered as an indicator for processes of organismal senescence. Moreover, the study offered a figure signifying the psychological impact on Telomere biology (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Psychological factors effect on TL biology in Athletes (Mehrsavar et al., 2020).

To overcome psychological stressors, Leprince et al., (2018) introduced four primary communal coping strategies: relationship-focused coping (e.g., social joining, motivational support, analysis, and action planning), problem-focused communal efforts (e.g., analysis and action planning, information sharing);

communal management of emotions (e.g., interpersonal emotional regulation, and reassurance); and communal goal withdrawal (e.g., task-disengagement, emotional venting).

Physiologically, genetic predispositions play a very important role in determining athletes' muscle traits and responses toward specific exercises. The genetic variants that impact traits like lean mass and muscle function can strongly influence the athlete's capacity for force generation and elasticity, which will eventually lead to affecting their overall performance (Klimentidis et al., 2016; Maciejewska-Skrendo et al., 2020).

Exercise, particularly aerobic, resistance, and anaerobic training, proved itself as a potent tool in combating the effects of aging on athletes. Aerobic exercise demonstrated many physiological benefits, which include improved cardiovascular function, cognitive function, insulin sensitivity, and overall muscle health (Carrick-Ranson et al., 2014; Tseng et al., 2013; Grosicki et al., 2021). Resistance training proved itself a very valuable tool in mitigating age-related muscle decline, activating molecular pathways essential for muscle adaptation and strength gains in older athletes (Hurley et al., 2011; Huebner et al., 2020). High-intensity interval training (HIIT) and sprint training also show a good effect in preserving insulin sensitivity and improving bone strength in aging athletes (Herbert et al., 2017; Korhonen et al., 2012). However, caution is necessary because certain high-level training or competition regimes, especially in swimming, might result in unfavorable effects on telomere length and subsequent biological aging, particularly in females (Nickels et al., 2021). Recovery strategies

play a very important role in maintaining older athletes' performance and well-being. Tailored recovery tactics, including monitoring biological markers, adequate sleep, and passive recovery strategies like compression garments and hydrotherapy, are necessary for improving recovery rates among aging athletes (Fell and Williams, 2008; Cullen et al., 2021). On the hormonal level, Both aerobic and resistance training can affect IGF-1 concentrations, which leads to possible anti-aging benefits, as it affects muscle growth and anabolic process (Saghiv et al., 2017; Nowak, 2010). Exercise-induced changes in growth hormone (GH) levels are different based on exercise type and intensity, which may result in a mitigation of age-related effects like muscle loss and frailty (Sellami et al., 2019). Testosterone, as an anabolic hormone, shows elevated levels in elite master athletes when compared to sedentary individuals, correlating with improved exercise capabilities (Hayes et al., 2013; Barbosa et al., 2021). Insulin levels and sensitivity have a strong link with exercise duration and intensity, with longer-term interventions showing potential for reducing fasting insulin levels and improving insulin action (Sellami et al., 2019; Kirwan et al., cited in Sellami et al., 2019). Endurance training is a very important preventive measure against age-related changes in insulin sensitivity and glucose tolerance (Strasser et al., 2021; Seals et al., 1984).

Recent medical advancements, including hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT), electronic equipment integration, and regenerative medicine, have a very supportive role in optimizing athlete recovery and performance. HBOT showed very promising results in muscle healing, recovery, and cognitive functions in athletes (Oyaizu et al., 2018; Maroon, 2022). The use of "Electronic Equipment" was not directly associated with anti-aging, but still it aids in monitoring training

load, injury prevention, and rehabilitation, which help athletes maintain peak performance (Hamstra-Wright et al., 2021). Regenerative medicine, involving treatments like stem cell therapies and platelet-rich plasma, has enough potential to deal with musculoskeletal injuries and age-related tissue degeneration, which facilitates tissue repair and functional recovery (Pang et al., 2017; Sepúlveda et al., 2015).

LIMITATIONS

A high degree of heterogeneity was found in this meta-analysis, which may have resulted from variations in the tissue (saliva, blood, and muscle), sample size, and telomere length assessment techniques (FISH, southern blot, and qPCR). There are also very few complete experimental investigations that have looked into the mechanisms of telomere preservation in master athletes, which made it challenging to pinpoint the exact cause of aging. There was no quantitative method to assess the recent medical advances on athletes and their relationship to aging due to lack of research in this field. So, a future clinical trial should be conducted on athletes to evaluate a more complete set of age-related markers, including oxidative stress, inflammatory markers, hormones, shielding proteins, and other aging markers, with the variables included in this study.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that aging has a complex effect on the physical, mental, and performance of athletes. This effect differs according to the current age of the athlete, the sport practiced including the training routine, the selection of recovery methods, and the genetic predisposition. Still, The proper selection of training routine, effective recovery methods, improved psychological qualities, and the use

of medical advances can mitigate aging effects and preserve elite performance for a longer time than previously assumed.

Athletes have longer telomeres than their contemporaries who are not athletes.

This difference may be attributed to a decrease in chronic inflammation, body fat percent, and oxidative stress as well as an increase in telomerase activity. These results may be the consequence of a mix of lifestyle factors, such as stress reduction, appropriate recovery, improved psychological qualities, and the use of recent medical advances rather than just frequent physical training.

A table was designed to aid elite athletes through their anti-aging journey. This table includes steps that should be done to preserve the elite level of performance and mitigate the aging effect on athletes (Table 8). Also, recommendations were written for the same purpose.

Generally, the benefits of various exercises, psychological interventions, and medical advances were outlined to provide a practical tool to mitigate aging.

Applying this knowledge by following the table designed to mitigate the aging effects may result in the preservation of elite performance and mitigate aging.

However, clinical trials on athletes in the age range of 30 to 35 years old are needed to understand the aging effect on performance and mitigate the early retirement of elite athletes.

Recommendations

- Maintain high training volume and intensity, though at a slightly reduced level compared to younger athletes (Foster et al., 2007)
- Focus on strength training, power training, and resistance training to offset age-related declines in muscle mass and power (Foster et al., 2007)
- Perform high-intensity interval training to maintain aerobic fitness and cardiovascular health (DeVan & Seals, 2012)
- Prioritize recovery through adequate nutrition, hydration, and sleep to facilitate training adaptations (Foster et al., 2007)
- Perform balance and proprioceptive training exercises to maintain coordination, stability, and injury resistance (Sazdova, 2019)
- Undergo regular medical screening to identify and manage any age-related health conditions that could impact training (Brukner et al., 2004)
- Learn and use coping skills, which include emotional awareness, self-management, and adaptive strategies to deal with psychological distress (Leprince et al., 2018)
- Elite athletes should develop recovery strategies to find balance in their careers, plan and structure their everyday lives effectively, and balance the demands of their sport with their social, family, and educational lives (Braun-Trocchio et al., 2022).
- Optimizing sleep duration and quality is crucial for maintaining physiological health in athletes (Leeder et al., 2012) if you have sleep disturbances, this may be an indicator of cognitive or physiological arousal (Gupta et al., 2017; Gupta et al., 2017).

- Elite athletes may benefit from specific training techniques aimed at improving fatigue resistance and enhancing endurance performance (Hawley et al., 1997). These techniques can help counteract age-related declines in physiological function.
- Always use HBO therapy to speed up recovery from muscle and tendon injury as it proved to be effective since the early 1980s (Horie et al., 2014)
- Integrate Electromyostimulation (EMS) in your training, the recommended is to undergo 2.8 to 3.3 sessions per week of training to improve various strength parameters. (Filipovic et al., 2011).
- Use wearable devices to monitor physiological variables, such as sleep patterns and respiratory rate, as it has gained interest in promoting health and improving exercise adherence among elite athletes (Taffoni et al., 2018; Driller et al., 2023).

Table 8. Athletic Anti-aging workflow

Goal: Mitigate Aging Effects on Performance	Due date/time	Comments
1. Establish Regular Exercise Routine		
a. Determine current fitness level		
b. Create a balanced routine		
c. Plan time for rest and recovery		
d. Monitor progress regularly		
2. Prioritize Recovery		
a. Set a consistent sleep schedule		
b. Create a restful environment		
c. Address potential sleep issues		
d. Get frequent massages		
e. Sauna bathing		
f. Daytime nap		

Goal: Mitigate Aging Effects on Performance	Due date/time	Comments
g. Use Cold Water Immersion (CWI)		
3. Include Strength Training		
a. Weight lifting		
b. Resistance band exercises		
c. Bodyweight exercises		
4. Maintain Flexibility and Balance		
a. Incorporate flexibility exercises in routine		
b. Practice balance exercises		
c. Consider Yoga or Pilates		
5. Stay Motivated		
a. Find an exercise buddy		
b. Set and achieve small goals		
c. Keep an exercise diary		
d. Mix it up; try new sports or exercises		
6. Regular Health Check-ups		
a. Routine check-ups with doctor		
b. Regular screening tests		
c. Keep up to date with vaccines		
7. Use Hyperbaric oxygen therapy		
a. Record performance before and after		
b. Record recovery state before and after		
8. Mental Wellness		
a. Practice mindfulness		
b. Seek support when needed		
c. Stay connected with loved ones		
d. Pursue hobbies outside of athletics		

Fig 10. Anti-aging scorecard for athletes to be used on a weekly basis

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